

NOTES

Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) with N,N,N',N'-tetramethylthiuramdisulphide

A. K. SRIVASTAVA*, R. K. AGARWAL, (MISS) VEENA KAPUR
and

P. C. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

Manuscript received 1 February 1982, revised 30 September 1982,
accepted 28 January 1983

A number of papers¹⁻³ on the ligand properties and redox reactions of thiurams have been published in recent years. N,N,N',N'-tetramethylthiuramdisulphide (Me₄tds) has four potential donor sites available for coordination to a metal ion but from steric considerations, it is expected to function either as a monodentate ligand coordinating through one of the thiocarbonyl sulphurs or as a bidentate ligand involving both the thiocarbonyl sulphurs.

N,N,N',N'-Tetramethylthiuramdisulphide (Me₄tds).

Recently, Contreas *et al*³⁻⁵ have characterized cobalt(II) chloride and chromium(III) chloride complexes of several thiuram ligands and have shown that tetramethylthiuramdisulphide coordinates in a bidentate manner through both the thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms resulting in the formation of a seven membered ring. Brinkhoff *et al* have reported Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes of tetrabutylthiuramdisulphide while Barrientos and Contreas⁶ reported the ir and Raman spectra of mercury(II) dihalide complexes of N,N,N',N'-tetramethylthiurammonosulphide. The present communication reports the preparation and infrared spectra of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes with N,N,N',N'-tetramethylthiuramdisulphide.

Experimental

N,N,N',N'-Tetramethylthiuramdisulphide (Aldrich) and other chemicals of analytical grade were used throughout.

Preparation of the complexes: An alcoholic solution of metal salt (0.01 mole in 20 ml ethanol) was mixed with a solution of the ligand (0.02 mole) dissolved in acetone (25 ml). This mixture was stirred for about 15 min and evaporated at room temperature. The resulting solid compounds were

washed with small amounts of absolute ethanol and finally with acetone. The compounds were recrystallised from acetone.

Analyses and physical measurements: The metal and anion contents of the complexes were determined by standard methods⁹. The elemental analyses were made at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The ir spectra of the complexes in KBr as well as in nujol mull were recorded on a Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer in the range 4,000-200 cm⁻¹. The molar conductances of 10⁻³ M nitrobenzene solutions were measured with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room temperature. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in PhNO₂.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) salts with Me₄tds results in the formation of complexes having the stoichiometry MX₂L [M=Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II); X=Cl, Br, NCS, CH₃COO, NO₃]. The analytical data indicate that the complexes are pure. The complexes are soluble in acetone, nitrobenzene, DMF and DMSO. They do not melt upto 250°. The conductances of the complexes in nitrobenzene are consistent with their non-electrolytic nature.

Infrared spectra: Table 1 contains the vibrational spectral data of N,N,N',N'-tetramethylthiuramdisulphide complexes in the four important regions viz., (a) 1550-1540 cm⁻¹, the so-called "thiureide band" (i.e., νC=N); (b) 1280-1240 cm⁻¹ the νC-N of the N-CH₃ group; (c) 1000-970 cm⁻¹ the νC=S and (d) a medium weak band in the 880-820 cm⁻¹ region due to the νCS involving the disulphide sulphur.

The band ca 400 cm⁻¹ can be easily assigned to the internal vibrational modes of the thiuramdisulphide ligand by comparison with previously reported complexes with the ligand^{3,4,8}. Table 1 shows the pertinent ir data of thiuram complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II).

The frequency of the 'thiureide band' is assigned to C=N stretching mode because its value is intermediate between C-N stretching (1350-1250 cm⁻¹) and the C=N stretching (1690-1640 cm⁻¹).

The ν(M-Cl) vibration has been assigned in the region (255-220 cm⁻¹)¹⁰.

The bonding mode of the thiocyanate in a complex can be established from the positions of the three fundamental vibrational modes (i.e., νCN, νCS and δNCS or δSCN). The infrared spectra of zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes show N-bonded thiocyanate group^{12,13}, and in mercury(II) complex it is terminally S-bonded^{14,15}. The infrared spectra of

* For correspondence.

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF Zn(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES OF N,N,N',N'-TETRAMETHYLTHIURAMDISULPHIDE

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	Other vibrations
Zn(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1540 (s,br)	1250 (s)	960 (s)	879 (w)	240 ($\nu\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}$)
Zn(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1480 (m)	1235 (s)	980 (m)	850 (m)	
Zn(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1500 (s)	1240 (s)	970 (s)	—	
Zn(Me ₄ tds)(NCS) ₂	1500 (s)	1235 (m)	970 (s)	860 (w)	2040, 2075(νCN), 800(νCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1510 (s)	1240 (s)	958 (s)	800 (w)	450 (δNCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1500 (s,br)	1240 (s)	970 (s)	850 (s)	—
Cd(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1500 (s,br)	1240 (m)	975 (s)	850 (s)	
Cd(Me ₄ tds)(NCS) ₂	1510 (m)	1235 (s)	970 (s)	845 (s)	2060(νCN), 830(νCS), 490(δNCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)(CH ₃ COO) ₂	1500 (m)	1240 (s)	950 (s)	850 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1530 (m,br)	1230 (s)	960 (s)	850 (w)	255($\nu\delta\text{Hg}-\text{Cl}$)
Hg(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1505 (m)	1250 (s)	965 (s)	855 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1510 (s,br)	1240 (s)	960 (s)	850 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)(SCN) ₂	1490 (m,br)	1242 (m)	960 (s)	875 (w)	2125(νCN), 720(νCS), 450(δSCN)
Hg(Me ₄ tds)(NO ₃) ₂	1540 (m,br)	1250 (s)	955 (s)	840 (w)	270($\nu\text{Hg}-\text{SCN}$)

mercury(II) nitrate complex show a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complex¹⁰⁻¹⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

References

- H. C. BRINKHOFF, J. A. CRASS, J. J. STEGGERDA and J. WILLAVE, *Reconol*, 1970, 89, 11.
- I. OJIMA, T. ONISHI, T. IWAMOTO and K. TAMAN, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 65.
- J. G. CONTRAS and H. CORTES, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 225.
- J. G. CONTRAS and H. CORTES, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 639.
- J. G. CONTRAS and H. CORTES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 1337.
- H. C. BRINKHOFF and J. M. A. DAHIZENBERG, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1972, 91, 117.
- H. CARBACHO and L. VICTORINA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 1327.
- C. F. BARRIENTOS and J. G. CONTRAS, *Anales De Quimica*, 1979.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", 1961.
- J. R. FERRARO, C. CRISTALLINI and G. ROCH, *Ric. Sci.*, 1968, 38, 433.
- J. L. BURMEISTER in 'Chemistry and Biochemistry of Thiocyanic Acid and its Derivatives', (Ed.) H. A. NEWMAN, Academic Press, London, 1975, Chapter 2, p. 68; H. A. NORBURY, *Advan. Inorg. Radio Chem.*, 1975, 17, 231.
- P. P. SINGH and S. A. KHAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 14, 143.
- J. LEWIS, R. S. NYHOLM and P. H. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4590.
- I. S. AHUJA and R. SINGH, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1974, 10, 421; I. S. AHUJA, R. SINGH and C. P. RAI, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1978, 8, 177.
- R. A. BAILEY, S. L. KOZAK, J. W. MIDULESEN and W. N. MILLS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 6, 407; I. S. AHUJA and A. GARG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1929, 2074.
- C. C. ADDISON and B. M. GATEHOUSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 613.
- F. H. JARDINE, A. G. VOHRA and F. J. YOUNG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 2941.
- H. J. GYSLING in "Inorg. Synth", (Ed.) D. F. SHRIVER, Wiley, N. Y., Vol. XIX, p. 98.

Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with *p*-Hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide

(Miss) K. DAS, U. S. PRASAD, A. K. DUBEY,

B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 12 November 1981, revised 5 November 1982, accepted 10 March 1983

COMPLEXES of some transition metals with thiohydrazide derivatives have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻³ and other workers⁴⁻⁷. In present paper we are reporting the complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide (phphH).

p-Hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide is a potent nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen donor ligand and can coordinate as neutral, monoanionic and dianionic ligand in thione-thiol tautomers A and B. However, in neutral or acidic medium it coordinates as simple thiohydrazide¹⁻⁷.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by reported method⁸. The metal salts and chemicals used were of B. D. H., AnalaR grade reagent.

Preparation of complexes :

[Ni(phphH)₂]₂X₂, (X = Cl, NO₃ or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄): Methanolic solution of hydrated nickel(II) salt (0.01 mol in 50 ml) was treated with 5% solution of the ligand dissolved in hot methanol. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 2-3 by adding a few drops of appropriate acid when orange-yellow to orange-red complex salt separated slowly. The product was filtered, washed with a little methanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.